

REGULATION OF OPEN BANKING (OPEN BANKING) IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotation: The article covers the topic of regulation of open banking (open banking) in the conditions of digital economy. Moreover historical background of Open banking were opened.

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Digital banking is present almost everywhere in the world, with incumbents, fintechs, and new digital banks offering accessible and efficient banking experiences (see sidebar “What is a digital bank?”). Given the relative immaturity of the digital-banking business model, regulators have awarded few (two to eight) licenses at a time. Just five years after launch, Tencent-backed WeBank serves 200 million people, and Alibaba-supported MYbank has more than 20 million small and medium-size enterprises (SMEs) as customers. In China, digital banks now have a 5 percent share of the market for unsecured consumer loans. South Korea’s KakaoBank, launched in 2017, attracted more than ten million customers in its first year. In June 2021, the company announced plans to raise \$2.3 billion in an initial public offering. Open Banking is a pioneering initiative designed to increase competition and innovation in the UK’s banking market. It is the first significant attempt to use technology to rebalance markets in favour of consumers. Its objective is to allow bank customers to securely share their data with third parties so a broad range of businesses can compete to provide bank customers with better financial services, more choice and lower prices. The UK is

already recognised as the global leader in this space and has the potential to develop Open Banking into a cornerstone of the UK’s digital economy Open Banking was mandated by the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) in its Retail Banking Market Investigation Order 2017 (the CMA Order) following its investigation into competition in UK banking. The CMA expects it to stimulate innovation across the financial sector, to enable the “unbundling” of complex retail banking products (in particular personal and business current accounts), and to ultimately lead to greater competition overall.

Giving consumers and businesses control over their data, it is hoped, will help them access better rates on overdrafts, savings, credit cards and mortgages, top up savings more easily, save money on foreign exchange, and help those with thin credit files get access to credit. It could help merchants to reduce the cost of accepting payments, by providing an alternative to credit and debit cards. And in time it may also allow customers to easily access better deals in other sectors like energy, telecoms and insurance. The initial phase of Open Banking implementation began in early 2018 and will finish in September 2019. It is too early to assess the impact of a major initiative like Open Banking, not least because the banks have not yet fully completed implementation[1]. Nonetheless the foundations have been established successfully, in particular the API standards and trust framework, and these were widely praised by our interviewees. Many other countries are using these standards as a blueprint for their own Open Banking projects.

Over the last two decades, businesses have used data, complex pricing and other tools to slice and dice consumers. This “yield management” by business is experienced as price discrimination, upselling, reduced choice and lock-in by consumers. This harms competition and may be turning people against markets. Open Banking is the first serious attempt to use technology to redress this problem. It focuses on the demand side in banking to empower consumers to compare banking products and switch more easily between them. By giving them

control over their financial data, it should also help them access products from third parties more easily. When Fingleton Associates and the Open Data Institute wrote our 2014 report for the Treasury proposing Open Banking, we hoped that it would empower bank customers to pick and choose the products that worked for them, and put consumers in control of their financial lives. A lot has been achieved in Open Banking's first year. The technical standards have been designed well and are popular with the businesses that use them, and customer adoption is growing. Over a hundred companies are now regulated to use the APIs. They offer services that range from account management, to financial advice to those in trouble, to credit referencing for people looking to borrow money. Open Banking is only the start. Similar projects may bring greater competition to markets like energy, telecoms and insurance, and drive switching between suppliers in those markets, and allow third party technology companies to use data for consumers' own benefit. If we get it right, we may see a great unbundling of complex product offers, and help consumers to make sense of previously unintelligible markets. For that to work, though, we need to get Open Banking right. The proposals in this report should go a long way towards realising the potential of Open Banking, satisfying the CMA's competition objectives, and making the banking market work for consumers above all[2].

For regulators weighing digital banking's benefits and risks, the challenge is to find the right balance between supporting innovation and protecting consumers. In addition, some jurisdictions, including Singapore and Malaysia, have used licensing regimes to support broader policy ambitions, such as boosting financial inclusion or increasing competition in specific segments. Currently, most jurisdictions apply existing banking laws and regulations to digital start-ups and fintechs. However, several jurisdictions have opted to build regulatory frameworks specifically for digital banking. There is no uniform formula or proposition. Business models—as expected—are often aligned with licensing conditions, which guide how banks can launch and develop. UK digital bank

Monzo started as an e-payments player, in line with its license, and later broadened its offering when it obtained a full banking license. China's MYBank and the United Arab Emirates' Anglo-Gulf Trade Bank focused from the start on lending and trade finance, respectively, as their banking licenses permitted[3].

In addition, the adoption and acceptance of various technological developments by regulators across geographies have allowed incumbent banks to modernize while setting the ground for digital banks and fully digital offerings to emerge. The following innovations and regulations enable or enrich digital offerings—both by traditional players and digital banks:

1. Electronic know your customer (e-KYC) enables fully digital onboarding, with stand-alone analytics checking customers' identities and conducting anti-money-laundering checks. Regulators can tailor identification methods based on their preferences.

2. E-signature allows customers to validate most types of transactions remotely.

3. Open banking offers network effects and fosters data sharing for better customer assessment and remote or automatic third-party transactions.

Ecosystem opportunities help nonbanks compete and allow consumers to benefit from broader and more personalized services. Cloud hosting can resolve three pain points for banks: infrastructure scaling, access to next-generation application architecture solutions, and the need to meet local regulations, such as those concerning local data hosting and protection[4]. The cloud also lowers barriers to entry by eliminating the need for upfront hardware purchases.

To sum up, it should be noted that A lot has been achieved in Open Banking's first year, and the groundwork has been laid for wide consumer adoption of many valuable use cases. Other sectors and countries are already using the Open Banking standards and trust framework as a blueprint for their own consumer-controlled data access regimes. However, for Open Banking to

really take off, the existing functionality needs to be expanded. The next stage should prioritise new use cases based on their value to consumers and provide both the basic plumbing at the technical layer and support for TPPs to develop services in the market. This will also support the potential for other sectors such as pensions to create similar initiatives. Open Banking has a bright future. As more products that use it roll out, and more consumers sign up to use them, we should see momentum building that strengthens the entire ecosystem and drives competition across the financial sector – and crucially, with consumers in control.

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